

Occurrence of Japanese Yam (*Dioscorea japonica*) as Vine Weed in Tea Gardens

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Received Date: 26-June-2022

Accepted Date: 28-July-2022

Published Date: 31-Aug-2022

Abstract

Dioscorea japonica (Japanese yam) is the most troublesome weed species of tea gardens in Japan. In recent years, effective integrated weed control methods in tea gardens that do not rely on hand weeding or herbicides have been sought, but the ecological properties of Japanese yam in tea gardens, and the basis for technological development, remain unclear. This study aimed to elucidate the actual occurrence, type of emergence, and characteristics of flowering of Japanese yam in tea gardens. The study observed emergence of many plants from propagules, whereas no plants from seeds were found. Additionally, many vines produced propagules, and only a few produced flowers, which were all female plants. This suggests that propagation of the Japanese yam in tea gardens is likely through clonal propagation by propagule, not by seed. Conversely, it was observed that half of the plants from propagule were in simple form, in which only the petiole and leaf blade are present without extending the above-ground stem, similar to forest floor plants. It is of concern that this type would be problematic as they are "reservoirs" for outbreaks in subsequent years.

Keywords: Japanese yam (*Dioscorea japonica*), vine weed, tea garden, propagule, tuber, forest floor plants

INTRODUCTION

Weeding reportedly takes 10–20% of the labor hours involved in tea garden management in Japan (Obata, 1987), particularly in organic tea garden farming, where weeding involves approximately 80% of labor hours (Ichihara et al, 2020).

Vine weeds are particularly problematic in tea gardens (Japan Soil Association, 2012). They thrive on the canopy of tea trees at harvesting height of tea leaves and become mixed in with tea leaves at harvest time. Because vine weeds grow within tea plants, it is difficult to control with herbicides; therefore, farmers have to individually pull out the vines by hand (Seo, 2012). In Shizuoka Prefecture (one of Japan's major tea producing districts), vine weeds, such as *Dioscorea japonica*, *D. tokoro*, *Trichosanthes cucumeroides*, and *Paederia foetida*, are problematic in tea gardens, with the most dominant weed species being *D. japonica* (Japanese yam) (Seo, 2016; Ichihara et al, 2020).

The Japanese yam is a perennial plant of Dioscoreaceae that is widely found at forest margins and in forests in Japan (Hori, 1984). *Dioscorea* plants, including *D. japonica*, are used for food globally (1994: Bhattacharjee, 2011; Ranjana, 2011, Wanasundera and Ravindran). In Japan, *D. polystachya* has been cultivated for vegetable. In contrast, *D. japonica* (Japanese yam) has long been traditionally collected from natural habitat and used as food. Presently, it is cultivated in Shizuoka Prefecture; therefore, the Japanese yam has characteristics of a food crop. Contrarily, the Japanese yam is a serious weed in tea gardens. Traditionally, weed control in tea gardens has relied on hand weeding. Recently, however, owing to the increase in organic farm production and expansion of the cultivation area of tea gardens, the lack of labor for weed control has become a serious problem in Japan. Therefore, it is a need to develop efficient weed management methods for tea gardens that incorporate IWM (Integrated Weed Management) (Ichihara et al, 2022).

To develop weed management methods in tea gardens, basic research on the physiological and ecological properties of Japanese yam is necessary. However, the actual status of the occurrence of Japanese yam has not been clarified. The present study aimed to investigate the type of emergence and characteristics of flowering of Japanese yam in tea gardens.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study field

The study was conducted in a tea garden at the Center for Education and Research in Field Sciences, Shizuoka University (Kariyado, Fujieda city, Shizuoka Prefecture, Japan; 34°54'18.8" N, 138°16'19.7" E). The site contains tea trees that were cultivated by conventional farming methods since 1974. The study area consisted of three rows of 6 m each in a tea garden where 'Yabukita' variety is cultivated.

Type of emergence

The Japanese yam reproduces using three methods: seed, propagule, or tuber. Individuals were counted by categorizing all the yam plants in the study area into three groups: plants from seeds, plants from propagules, and plants from tubers. The survey was conducted on August 7, 2020.

Characteristics of flowering

Fifty vines of Japanese yam were collected and surveyed for presence of flowers and propagule. The survey was conducted on August 20, 2020.

Observation of Japanese yam tubers under the tea tree

Roots of the tea tree were pulled out of the soil to reach the Japanese yam tubers. Six tuber samples were weighed using a electronic digital scale. This survey was conducted on October 23, 2020.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The plants of Japanese yam typically grow from seeds, propagules, and tubers. Percentages of plants that emerged from seeds (0%), propagule (45.4%), and tubers (54.6%) in the tea garden are represented in Fig. 1.

Two plant types emerged from propagule: a type that extends vines (the elongation type) and a type that does not extend vines but produces a single leaf (the floor type) under tea trees (Fig. 2). This simple floor-type form, in which only the petiole and leaf blade are present without extending the above-ground stem, is often observed in forest floor plants that grow naturally in forests with little sunlight, such as *Asarum caulescens*, *Erythronium japonicum*, and *Lilium japonicum* (Fukada *et al.*, 2000; Inagaki, 2003; Kawano, 1984; Takasu, 2001). Among the individuals derived from propagule, the occurrence rates of the floor and elongation types were 21.8% and 23.6%, respectively, and the incidence of the two types was at about the same level. It was previously observed in natural forest habitats of Japanese yam that there is a type of young plant, which has only one leaf without vine (Hori, 1984). The present study demonstrated that a floor type with only one leaf exists in tea gardens as in forests.

Conversely, the seed dispersal mode of Japanese yam is Anemochory using pterometeorochory mechanism (Hori, 1984; Tateno, 1995; Minami and Azuma, 2003). Therefore, it has been concerned the seeds of Japanese yam are dispersed by wind and invade tea gardens (Japan Soil Association, 2012). However, no plants from seed were observed, while many plants from propagule were observed in this study. Thus result suggests Japanese yam invasion in tea gardens through seed is a rare case and is mainly spread through propagules. Furthermore, approximately half of the plants from propagules were floor type. A major concern about weeds in tea gardens is that they often grow taller than the tea plants and are mixed with the tea leaves at harvest. Although the floor type does not cause direct damage to tea plantations because it does not extend vines, it is difficult to detect and control because it grows at the base of tea trees. Therefore, it is possible that these floor types would be problematic as "reservoirs" for outbreaks in subsequent years.

The percentages of propagules, flower attachments, and male and female flowering (dioecy) on Japanese yam vines that grew in the tea garden is presented in Table 1. In the study area, 84% of the vines had neither flowers nor propagule. However, 14% of the vines attached only propagule and 2% attached female flowers. No vines were observed that attached both female flowers and propagule, and none attached male flowers, supporting that Japanese yam in tea gardens is not propagated by seed but by clonal propagation.

Photographs of a tuber of Japanese yam dug up in the tea garden are shown in Fig. 3. Since tubers of Japanese yam grow under tea trees, its ecological traits are unknown. In this present study, Japanese yam tubers were collected from under tea trees while pulling out the tea trees roots. The Japanese yam tubers are long and slender and characterized by straight underground growth (Iida, 2001), contrarily, it is known that presence of pebbles in soil causes increased branching (Kawakami, 1968; Iida, 2001). The present study observed that the Japanese yam tubers intertwined with the tea tree roots, forming a multi-branched shape,

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since the roots of the tea trees were spreading close to the ground surface. Although the Japanese yam is a perennial plant, the tuber does not grow for multiple years because nutrients in the tubers are used up in one year for above-ground growth and formation of new potatoes. The weights of the six tubers dug up in this study were 284, 180, 106, 76, 68, and 64 g, respectively.

Thus, the Japanese yam tubers in the tea garden has a complicated shape and is intertwined with the roots of the tea plant. Additionally, many branches tend to break off when forcible digging is attempted. Therefore, it is considered difficult to control disease when Japanese yam tubers are dug.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated that 1) most of the young Japanese yam plants originated from propagules, 2) many vines produced propagule, and only a few produced flowers, and 3) the few flowers were all attached to female plants. Although it was a common opinion that Japanese yam spreads through wind-dispersed seeds, this study's results indicate that clonal propagation by propagule is main reproduction method of Japanese yam in tea gardens. Since ecological properties of plants from propagules of Japanese yam are unknown, this study provides a basis for future research on their growth in the laboratory and experimental field.

Additionally, this study found the half of the plants from propagules were simple form, in which only the petiole and leaf blade are present without extending the above-ground stem, similar to structures of forest floor plant. It is a major concern that this type would be problematic as they may serve as "reservoirs" for outbreaks in subsequent years. Typically, vine weed control in tea gardens is done by hand, and currently, machines are being developed to remove the vines. However, complete vine removal is difficult, and reserve 'floor type' remains under the tea tree after the vine removal process. Therefore, in developing machinery, it might be desirable to consider a weeding robot that weeds under the tea plants.

Acknowledgments

We gratefully acknowledge the work of past and present members of our laboratory. This work was supported by Fujieda city.

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Fig.1 The floor type of Japanese yam in tea garden, which does not extend vines but produces a single leaf.

Fig.2 Frequency of each type of Japanese yam emerging in tea gardens.

Table 1 Frequency of propagule and female and male flower attachments on Japanese yam vines in tea gardens (n=50)

	Frequency (%)
No flowers and ropagule	84.0
Only ropagules	14.0
Female flowers and ropagules	0.0
Only female flowers	2.0
Male flowers and ropagules	0.0
Only male flowers	0.0

Fig. 3 Tuber of Japanese yam dug up from under a tea plant.